

Determinants of Sustainability of Donor Funded Project in Arid and Semi-Arid Lands in West Pokot County, Kenya

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Abstract

The purpose of the study was to investigate the Determinants of Sustainability of Donor Funded Project in Arid and Semi-Arid Lands in Kenya. Case Of West Pokot County, Kenya. The descriptive survey research design was employed in the study. From the target population of 159 employees, the study used a simple random sampling technique to select a sample size of 114. The study used five point structured questionnaires and document analysis as the main tools for collecting data. Cronbach Alpha Coefficient indicator was used to test the internal consistency of the items. Data were analysed using both descriptive and inferential analysis. Descriptive methods such as frequencies mean and standard deviation were used to provide general trends of the data. Inferential statistics included Pearson correlations to show the relationship between variables. Findings showed that budget plan and Technical expertise have a significant effect on the sustainability of donor funded projects. Technical expertise, which is a function of education and experience, has a positive and significant effect on the Sustainability Of Donor Funded Projects. Therefore, human capital represents potential areas where partnerships can enhance the overall Sustainability Of Donor Funded Projects by ensuring that the employees have the requisite skills needed

Keywords: Sustainability, Donor Funded, Project, budget plan, Technical expertise

1. Introduction

To ensure a stable and sustainable economy that is attributed with double digit growth on its Gross domestic product figure (GDP), it was important to ensure that community development projects are fully supported by various stake holders these including donors' international agencies to projects that need considerable little amounts money but have a great impact in transforming the prospects of the economy. The past two decades have witnessed an increase in official aid to NGOs, with the United States contributing nearly 50% of the funds to NGOs. Between 10 -15% (approximately 6 billion dollars) in support of development projects and programs through various NGOs (ODI, 1996). From 1975 to 1988, the level of total overseas development assistance increased by 43% from the US \$ 27.3 to 48.2 billion, 11% growth from 27.3 to 30 billion dollars and between 1980 to 1988, and the amount of aid allocated to NGOs rose from US\$1.04 to 2.13 billion (Alan Fowler, 1992).

While much of the development aid comes as financial assistance to the state budget (Moyo 2009), donor funded projects are yet another channel through which development aid gets to the developing countries. Donor funded projects provide the channel for expatriates and other resources and many keep mushrooming day by day, showing the large extent to which development aid is getting to the developing countries. However, while this aid has been provided in large quantities, the debt burden and poverty levels in developing countries, especially Sub Saharan Africa, seem to be on the increase and the ability of aid to solve this is highly questioned (Erixon, 2005).

Several sponsors from the West harmoniously decided on the intent of collaborating with emergent nations as opposed to doing things to third world nations. Some replaced the term, "technical assistance" with 'technical cooperation' and started collaborating with emergent national governments, which, at that period were considered the fundamental drivers of economic growth, to expand their capacity to achieve the livelihood needs of the local people. This was in line with the 'Basic Needs' strategy that pioneered in the World Bank but is more often than not linked to the International Labor Office (ILO). According to the ILO (1997), the

framework was created to end poverty through championing economic growth that is governed by the state with equity through the institution of allocation of revenue systems for instance education and public health as well as other needed social amenities with consideration to public needs and choices. It was well backed by a majority of the official development assistance community, in addition to various NGOs that turned out to be significant drivers for remitting relief assistance to countries that had fallen; and the government fell short of functional management of its region during this stipulated time. Indeed this was the situation until the strategy contradicted the growth of a new economic tradition in Western Countries that went on to override the development project during the 1980s.

Donors are the key policy makers when it comes to worldwide advancement sine they fund most of the projects. Nonetheless, external assistance is not translated directly from benefactors to target groups, instead it undergoes a cycle from several persons and affiliated establishments in what can be coined as an ‘aid-delivery chain’ that has grown complicated ever since the 1990s. There exists a high level of fund allocation without accurate accountability on what the funds are aimed at alleviating nor sufficient auditing of what help the money being given is to donor sponsored projects. Furthermore, several projects fall short of expediency causing them to collapse shortly upon starting. Nevertheless, a scarce number of sponsors have clearly established their backing for democratic leadership; the rationale steering their assistance programs was that political deregulation gives rise to economic loosening and in turn creating a domino effect.

There is no significant effect of Technical Expertise on Sustainability Of Donor Funded Projects

There is no significant effect of Budgetary Plan On Sustainability Of Donor Funded Projects

1.1 Theoretical Framework

A theory of change is the articulation of the underlying beliefs and assumptions that guide a service delivery strategy and are believed to be critical for producing change and improvement. Theories of change represent beliefs about what is needed by the target population and what strategies will enable them to meet those needs (INSP Working group, 2005). They establish a context for considering the connection between a system’s mission, strategies and actual outcomes, while creating links between who is being served, the strategies or activities that are being implemented, and the desired outcomes.” A theory of change has two broad components. The first component of a theory of change involves conceptualizing and operationalizing the three core frames of the theory. The second component of a theory of change involves building an understanding of the relationships among the three core elements and expressing those relationships clearly. The theory of change is defined by the three core elements and the relationship that exists between them (INSP Working group, 2005).

Theories of change help move stakeholders from being passive collectors and reporters of information to active users of the information for system planning and service delivery. Theories of change help system and program staff better understand the kind of evaluation information they need to make day-to-day decisions. Theories of change help the evaluator develop research questions that focus measurement on changes that can occur given the particular strategies that are operative at the system, program, and client level. Because they facilitate understanding the link between strategies and the achievement of outcomes, theories of change facilitate the integration of data from broader evaluation and accreditation requirements into local evaluation efforts. Stakeholders in a group setting, such as a formally facilitated meeting, solicit input, gather insights, and brainstorm through the stages of new program development. Individually or with colleagues, to develop a Theory of Change to launch a new initiative; to redirect efforts in a present area of funding or to assist in the decision process regarding working in new areas (Norland,2005). One theory of change is The Equilibrium Theory of Social Change (Talcott, 1966) they are also called functional theories as they see society as made up

of parts that are functional in sustaining society. Society is seen as made up of sub-systems that are constantly moving in unison towards stabilizing sustaining the society. A change in one part leads to a compensatory change in other parts until the entire social system returns to some level of stability or equilibrium.

The colonialists introduced a new (though limited) western education meant to make the natives fit in with the new colonial order. The education was necessary to instill conformity; for socialization (“talk the same language”); and also enable the native's service the new order as junior officials. The change in education brought about changes in all other aspects of life – thus reinforcing stability and equilibrium in the new order. A complete new value system now exists in Africa due to the introduction of this western education. For example, new systems of law and order and administrative systems were instituted as the idea about the nuclear family and also the whole concept of individualism was supported by the western education system. Western education also facilitated the introduction and spread of Christianity. The ability to read the Quran also has had a major effect on the spread of Islam in Africa.

2. Literature review

2.1 Technical Expertise and Sustainability Of Donor Funded Projects

Bowen, (2004) concluded that technical expertise from donor funded projects is not just the people working in an organization. It's a broad combination of their experience, attitudes, abilities, culture etc. For more than three decades researchers from the areas of HRM have been interested in finding the relationship between human capital which includes education, knowledge, experience, and skills and the success of a project. A Number of researches suggest positive relationships between human capital and the success of a project. The human capital which consists of current task-related knowledge and skills has a positive relationship with the success of a project (Edward, 2007).

According to Adhazi, (2004) when it comes to the technical expertise aspects of the health sector challenges in service delivery, all countries are equally concerned. The severe and acute shortage of personnel has been profusely documented through reports and papers by prominent figures of the health development world such as WHO, GHWA, and numerous international organizations, think tanks, institutions and civil society representatives. The shortage of personnel leads to low delivery of health services.

There are many issues in implementation; however, of central importance is technical expertise. technical expertise can be viewed as a function of education and experience. If these are deficient, there is a high probability that a project mission will be inappropriately specified from the outset, with the result that time, cost and quality targets will be compromised from the beginning. If this is the case, it is highly improbable that the resource base will be organised and mobilised to deliver time, cost and quality targets successfully (Nubi, 2001).

Evaluating the knowledge and skill attributes of individuals and of organisations is an area addressed by human capital (HC) theory. HC theory addresses the *worth* of an organisation's human resource base in the context of project performance. HC focuses on the value that is added to an organisations business, ultimately in terms of profitability, solely by its stock of human resources (Thomas, 2002).

Gibson, (2001) argues that a project's performance will be influenced by its human capital is not a new concept. In theory, the higher a firm's stock of human capital, the more successful the project will be and the greater its competitive advantage over its rivals will be, and *vice versa*. The strategic importance of HC in terms of achieving enhanced performance is now becoming increasingly recognized. However, despite this, a precise understanding of how significant HC's role is in determining performance, remains unclear, and is the subject of much research in various industries.

Other resources must be managed, but people represent the primary resource directly influenced by the activities of PM. If people are to be managed successfully, the project manager must rely on knowledge and experience. Working with people involves personal judgment and decision making that is not easily learned and cannot be solely based on systems or tools. A project manager needs to be more socially orientated than functional (Carmelli, 2009)

Health personnel shortage remains the key component of a massive health sector crisis suffered in many areas whether emerging or in development which leads to low service delivery. Its acute effects are entangled with the shortage of health staff faced by developed countries. This global context of free movement of workers and resources can impair health sector empowerment strategies at the national level. Alternative analysis stress that this is only the tree hiding the forest: continuous underinvestment in public health systems, a weak economic growth context, appalling work conditions and infrastructures, deterrent salaries are to be closely looked at while a trend of skilled personnel migration towards more satisfactory and stimulating work and life environments is overwhelming all countries. This is a sensible concern that fuels an already robust debate about strategies coherence and legitimacy of external pressures. These push factors sometimes outweigh efforts that are made to strengthen the whole system (Chen. 2002).

Human resource components represent potential areas where partnerships can enhance the whole system's outcomes provided that coherence, efficiency and cost-effectiveness objectives have been drawn up and integrated into a strategic framework beforehand, thus improving efficient service delivery. As seen previously, triggers of this crisis are well identified. HR shortage in health lies at the heart of the health sector, strengthening the policy agenda. The bottom line argument is that if no sustainable investments are made one way or another, retaining health staff in appalling work conditions within systems that fail to deliver their services in an effective manner is going to be extremely difficult. More attractive work elements can easily be looked for in other countries (Beck, 2003).

2.2 Influence Of Budgetary Plan On Sustainability Of Donor Funded Projects

According to Austin, (2000) bidding for donor funded projects projects procurement is expensive. Often, the largest component of bid costs is designed, which can account for 50-60% of the total up from approximately 40% in 2005. Legal fees, on the other hand, have become less significant, dropping from 40% in 2005 to 10 12% currently. The efficiency of the budgetary process can significantly impact on efficient project performance because services are offered when needed.

There is the likelihood that managers may be tempted not to plan for future operations because of day to day pressures and operating challenges. The budgeting planning process ensures that managers do plan for future operations, and that they consider how conditions in the next year might change and what steps they should take now to respond to these changed conditions (Julia, 2010). The slack planning measures the differences between the subordinate's performance capability and the corresponding planning budget and, thus, is an ex ante measure of the planning error.

By setting a planning budget that is observable for the subordinate, the superior can signal to the subordinate which performance they expect. Goal-setting theory suggests that the planning budget can have a supporting effect on motivation. However, if the goal is too high or too low, as it will be with positive probability due to the information asymmetry, the planning budget may have a negative effect because it undermines goal acceptance (Arnold and Gillenkirch, 2009). Moreover, setting a challenging goal that is achievable in less than 50% of the cases is not compatible with the optimal planning budget that should be set to the expected performance capability. Consequently, the role of the planning budget as a second goal for the subordinates is unclear, and we do not provide a prediction.

The planning task may have a behavioural effect on the budget negotiation if the planning task draws the superiors' attention more strongly towards the subordinates' average performance capability

Wijewardena and De Zoysa (2001) in their study found a positive and significant relationship between budgeting planning and sales growth, and between budgeting planning and return on investment; however, they also found an insignificant relationship between budgeting planning and ROI. In addition, Fonseka and Perera (2004) similarly found the same results of a positive and significant relationship between budgeting planning and return on investment.

Yang Qi (2010) showed that the formal budgeting planning and the formal budgetary control show different patterns in terms of their effect on financial performance. The formal budgeting planning has a stronger impact on the growth of sales of SMEs, compared to the formal budgetary control

When setting a budget, members of the organization are supposed to participate in defining explicit budgetary goals and to be involved in subsequent revision to these goals with the management (Chalos & Poon, 2000) and when budget variance (s) occurs, participation and discussion among different levels of management facilitate and enable accurately identifying the possible reasons for such variance(s) and also the corresponding corrective actions to be taken. Therefore, budgetary participation refers to the involvement of managers in the budgetary process and their influence in the setting of budgetary targets (Subramaniam & Ashkanasy, 2001).

Joshi, et.al (2003), however, examine budgeting planning, control, and performance evaluation practices in a developing country. He conducts a questionnaire survey of 54 medium and large-sized firms including both the listed and non-listed firms located in Bahrain. His research finds that most of the firms prepare long-range plans and operating budgets, and use budget variances to measure a manager's performance, for "timely recognition of problems, and to improve the next period's budget". Additionally, there has been some discussion in the academic literature on the relationship between strategic planning and performance of SMEs (Arm & Cowen, 1990; Hillidge, 1990; Knight, 1993), but researchers have not paid considerable attention to the possible relationship between budgeting process and performance in SMEs (Wijewardena & De Zoysa, 2001). So the process of budgeting and its relationship with performance in SMEs are still unclear. Merchant (2002) points out that the budgeting process is adopted differently in firms that differ in the diversity of the organizational system. Accordingly, due to diversity, the budgeting process may differ. The issue of how budgeting in SMEs impacts their performance is, therefore, certainly worthwhile to be explored.

3. Material and methods

The study adopted an explanatory research design. The target population was 159 employees in the from 4 donor funded projects in west pokot County. From the target population of 159 employees, Yamane (1967:886) sample size formula and modified by Kent (2008) was used to select a sample size of 114 employees. The primary data on the other hand was obtained from questionnaires adopted and interview schedules and administered for the study. Cronbach's alpha instrument was used to determine reliability, where Cronbach's coefficient, having a value of more than 0.5 is considered adequate for such exploratory work (Nunally, 1978). From the test results above both findings were above 0.7, Ng'ang' an *et al* (2009) supports that correlation of 0.7 as an acceptable threshold, and thus the questionnaire will be considered to be reliable. In the analysis ratio scale was used in data measurement and both inferential and descriptive statistics were used to analyze the data. In descriptive statistics the study employed descriptive statistical tools more precisely SPSS which helped to describe the data and determine the extent used, use of graphs, pie charts and tables was used to present the data. Pearson correlation method has been used to assess' relationship between irrigation scheme and community development

4. Findings and Discussion

4.1 Sample characteristics

From the results, 35.5% (38) of the respondents were female and 64.5% (69) of them were male. The results indicate that male respondents comprise the majority. The data collected revealed that 43.9% of the respondents are over 35 years, 42.1% aged between 21 to 35 years and 11% were below 20 years old. The findings were Primary 5.6%, the secondary was 18.7%, Certificate was 19.6%, Diploma was 55.1% and those with a degree were 0.9%. From the findings, 39.3% (42) of the respondents have been in the project for 1 to 5 years, 35.5% (38) 6 to 10 years, 14% (15) 11 to 20 years and 11.2% (12) of them for over 21 years. From the foregoing, the respondents had high working experience and were relied upon to provide reliable data on the study problem.

Table 1 Demographic information

		Frequency	Percent
Gender	Male	69	64.5
	Female	38	35.5
	Total	107	100
Age bracket	Below 20 Yrs	15	11
	21-35yrs	45	42.1
	Above 35yrs	47	43.9
	Total	107	100
the highest level of education	Primary School	6	5.6
	Secondary School	20	18.7
	Certificate	21	19.6
	Diploma	59	55.1
	Degree	1	0.9
	Total	107	100
Years you in the projects	1-5	42	39.3
	6-10	38	35.5
	11-20	15	14
	Above 21	12	11.2
	Total	107	100

4.2 TECHNICAL EXPERTISE

The study sought to find out the technical expertise provided within donor funded projects model. The results are as presented in table 2. From the findings, The mean value of 3.79 was confirmation that the partners provide employees with expertise while the standard deviation of 0.821 further revealed less degree of variation in the responses. The item realized a mean of 3.43 and a standard deviation of 0.848 revealing that there was still doubt whether the partners provided employees with the necessary skills needed. The results summed up to a mean of 4.01 and a standard deviation of 0.841 an indication that their employees received allowances from their partners. This summed up to a mean of 3.74 and a standard deviation of 0.769. On the whole, their partners motivated their employees. The item realized a mean of 3.89 and a standard deviation of 0.805. It can therefore be inferred that employees in the project feel appreciated and recognized by their partners.

Table 2 Technical Expertise

	Mean	Std. Deviation
We have been giving employees with expertise from our partners	3.79	0.821
Our partners provided our employees with the necessary skills they need	3.43	0.848
Most of our employees receive allowances from our partners	4.01	0.841
Our partners motivate our employees	3.74	0.769
Employees in the projects feel appreciated and recognized by our partners	3.89	0.805

4.3 Budgetary Plan

The researcher also found it necessary to establish a budgetary plan. The findings are presented in table 3. In regards to whether all partners participate in the budgeting process, The results summed up to a mean of 3.76 and a standard deviation of 0.91 meaning that the majority of the partners participated in the budgeting process. The study further enquired from the respondents whether their partners' explanation is provided when the budget is revised. The results summed up to a mean of 3.93 and a standard deviation of 0.785. This implies that their partners' explanations are provided when the budget is revised. In relation to whether free discussions between partners on the budget are encouraged, The item realized a mean of 3.86 and a standard deviation of 0.806. Further, respondents were asked whether a contribution from partners to the budget viewed importantly. The results indicate that contributions from partners to the budget are viewed as important. The respondents were also asked whether opinions and/or proposals relating to the budget are challenged before the development of the budget, This means that it has not been fully established if opinions and/or proposals relating to the budget are challenged before the development of the budget. Finally, the study sought to find out if the communication of details of budget policy and guidelines to people responsible for the preparation of the budget is often made. The results summed up to a mean of 3.78 and a standard deviation of 0.945 indicating that there is the communication of details of budget policy and guidelines to those responsible.

Table 3 Budgetary Plan

	Mean	Std. Deviation
All partners participate in the budgeting process.	3.76	0.91
Our partners are explanation provided when the budget is revised.	3.93	0.785
Free discussions between partners on budget encouraged	3.86	0.806
Contribution from partners to the budget viewed importantly.	3.82	0.799
Opinions and / or proposals relating to the budget-challenged before the development of budget	3.47	0.925
Communication of details of budget policy and guidelines to people responsible for the preparation of budgets often made.	3.78	0.945

4.4 Sustainability of Donor Funded Projects

Table 4 presents the results on the Sustainability Of Donor Funded Projects . In relation to whether the project was completed in time. The item reported a mean of 3.47 meaning that the project was completed in time. The study further enquired from the respondents whether the project can now service its purpose. The results summed up to a mean of 3.67 and a standard deviation of 1.071. This implies that the project can now service its purpose. To establish whether most of their employees are always willing to serve. The results summed up to a mean of 3.52 and a standard deviation of 1.067 an indication that their employees are willing to serve. In order to ascertain whether employees can promptly respond to request even when busy. This summed up to a mean of 3.65 and a standard deviation of 0.953. Generally, the employees respond promptly even when they are busy.

Table 4 Sustainability of Donor Funded Projects

	Mean	Std. Deviation
The project was completed within the time	3.47	1.049
The project can now service its purpose	3.67	1.071
Most of our employees are always willing to serve	3.52	1.067
Employees can promptly response to our requests even when they are busy	3.65	0.953

4.5 Testing hypothesis

The study exhibited a strong relationship between budget plan and sustainability of donor funded projects ($r = 0.588$, p -value $< .01$). Additionally, there was a medium relationship between community support technical support and sustainability of donor funded projects ($r = 0.335$, p -value $< .01$). Table 4 illustrates the model summary of the multiple regression model, the results showed that all the four predictors (technical support, financial support) explained 51.3 percent variation of sustainability of donor funded projects (R squared = 0.513). Furthermore, study findings showed that technical support had coefficients of the estimate which was significant basing on $\beta_2 = 0.181$ (p -value = 0.017 which is less than $\alpha = 0.05$) hence we fail to accept the hypothesis and conclude that technical support has a significant effect on the sustainability of donor funded projects. This indicates that for each unit increase in technical support, there is up to 0.181 units increase in the sustainability of donor funded projects. The effect of technical support is stated by the t-test value = 2.415 which points out that the effect of technical support is twice that of the error associated with it. In line with the results, findings by CBI, (2007) indicate that donor funded projects are a long collaborative arrangement allowing for the combination of complementary skills and expertise of each partner, with interest in improving the quality of services. In direct support to the study findings, Edward, (2007) elucidates that the human capital which consists of current task-related knowledge and skills has a positive relationship with the success of a project. On the same note, Gibson, (2001) argues that a project's performance will be influenced by its human capital.

Findings showed that the budget plan had coefficients of the estimate which was significant basing on $\beta_3 = 0.294$ (p -value = 0.002 which is less than $\alpha = 0.05$) thus we fail to accept the hypothesis and conclude that budget plan has a significant effect on the sustainability of donor funded projects. This suggests that there is an up to 0.294 unit increase in the sustainability of donor funded projects for each unit increase in the budget plan. The effect of the budget plan is more than the effect attributed to the error, this is indicated by the t-test value = 3.111. In conformity with the results, Julia, (2010) echoes that budgeting planning process ensures that managers do plan for future operations, and that they consider how conditions in the next year might change and the necessary steps to be taken to counter the changed conditions. The results are also in tally with a study by Wijewardena and De Zoysa (2001) indicating that there are a positive and significant relationship budgeting planning and sales growth, and between budgeting planning and return on investment. Further support of the study findings is by Fonseka and Perera (2004) who also found a positive and significant relationship between budgeting planning and return on investment.

Table 5 Multiple Regression Results

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		Sig.	correlation zero-order
	B	Std. Error	Beta	T		
(Constant)	-0.966	0.558		-1.731	0.087	
technical support	0.288	0.119	0.181	2.415	0.017	.335**
budget plan	0.38	0.122	0.294	3.111	0.002	.588**
R Square	0.513					
Adjusted R Square	0.494					

a Dependent Variable: Sustainability Of Donor Funded Projects

5. Conclusion and recommendations

Technical expertise which is a function of education and experience has a positive and significant effect on the Sustainability Of Donor Funded Projects . As such, the provision of employees with expertise by partners is more likely to lead to the success of the project. Therefore, human capital represents potential areas where partnerships can enhance the overall Sustainability Of Donor Funded Projects by ensuring that the employees have the requisite skills needed. Additionally, the budget plan has a significant effect on efficient Sustainability Of Donor Funded Projects . This is due to the fact that services are offered when needed. Through budget planning, there is the communication of details of budget policy and guidelines to the individuals responsible for the preparation of the budget. The partners can therefore signal to them which performance they expect. Consequently, there is the participation of all members in defining the budgetary goals.

The study has established that technical expertise is instrumental in enhancing Sustainability Of Donor Funded Projects . Consequently, there is a need for partners to provide employees with the needed expertise to lead the project to success. Besides, it is important for partners to motivate the employees and make them feel appreciated and recognized. There is also a need for employees to receive allowances from their partners.

With respect to budget planning, it is utmost necessary for all partners to participate in the budgeting process. Partners' explanations need to be provided when the budget is revised. There is also a need for free discussions between partners and communication of details of budget policy and guidelines to those responsible for the preparation of the budget. Most importantly, the contribution from partners to the budget needs to be viewed importantly. Major contextual and settings to be considered in future researches should consider insights from this study influencing Sustainability Of Donor Funded Projects including the three factors: 1) *financial support*; 2) *technical expertise and budget planning* as playing an important role in enhancing Sustainability Of Donor Funded Projects .

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